

Combating gender stereotypes by highlighting women's contribution to the history of societies

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HerStory Methods Manual

Mapping the women footprint on local histories

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HerStory Consortium

Amendment History

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1. Introduction

The project HerStory aims to challenge the narrative that the field of history is male dominated by highlighting women's presence and contributions throughout history. The project aims to fill the gap of missing information about women's role in shaping society, as mainstream literature on women's history is limited and their contributions are often overlooked.

The research was conducted around 8 European cities, in 9 European countries. This document has been developed through the common effort of organisations and institutions from: Salamanca/Spain (University of Salamanca), Martinique/France (D' Antilles et D' Ailleurs), Nicosia/Cyprus (The Advisory Centre for the Support of the Family – SYKESO and Centre for Social Innovation – CSI Cyprus), Athens/Greece (Kyttaro Enallaktikon Anazitiseon Neon – KEAN), Sofia/Bulgaria (Infinite Opportunities Association – IOA), Velenje/Slovenia (University of Velenje – LUV), Vilnius/Lithuania (Diversity Development Group – DDG), Lecco/Italy (Specchio Magico Cooperativa Sociale Onlus).

Through a bottom-up research approach and the development of local multi-stakeholder networks, the consortium works towards enhancing the visibility of women in history and challenges the field of history in a gender-perspective way. During this research the consortium detected statues and historical areas that represent female figures in history, aiming to raise awareness about their contribution.

The desk research “Mapping the women footprint on local histories” seeks to investigate women’s triumphs and normalise the success of women through the publicity of women’s statues and monuments, street names, and historical places related to women’s presence in society. In this way, any historical misconceptions and misrepresentations can be addressed towards gender equality. The development of a European report on this specific field can fill the gap that exists in the history of European cities.

A European report is important in order to fill the gap of missing information regarding women’s footprint in history. The development of a Methods Manual document will enhance innovative actions which were suggested by interested actors in European societies, such as stakeholders in the field of gender studies and history and, of course, young people.

Such reports can contribute to changing the frame and the reflection of conclusive male patterns' impact on people. The outcomes of the research can provide knowledge and inspiration to young people and stakeholders around Europe. Finally, the results of the research will work as a source of information for the development of the transnational map where the visitors will be able to find remarkable places regarding women in history in all partner cities of the partnership.

2. Transnational collections of Methods

2.1. Spain

2.1.1. Method n.1: Rostros del Olvido (Faces of Oblivion)

Name of the organisation/association

The artists' collectives ID ARTE y Mujeres dos Rombos , CEMUSA, Salamanca City Council, the Junta de Castilla y León, the Casa de las Conchas

City, Country

Salamanca, Spain, 2023

Information about the organisation

ID ARTE artists' collective: Non-profit association for the promotion, knowledge and development of art and culture. It creates and organises innovative projects that enrich the cultural heritage and identity. It promotes education and participation through seminars, workshops, conferences, guided tours and activities that bring culture closer to society; with a social commitment and interest towards groups that can obtain from them the full development of their social, human and intellectual potential. It serves as a platform and link between institutions, artists, cultural agents and professionals, promoting national and international initiatives that make the country a point of reference and model of a new artistic and cultural development. (<https://www.idarte.org/rostros.php>)

Mujeres dos Rombos: Mujeres Dos Rombos is a Contemporary Artistic Activism that seeks to generate awareness through the sensorial experience that implies a positioning of the spectator before the artistic work, in which emotion is a fundamental factor (<https://www.mujeresdosrombos.com/>).

CEMUSA: The Women's Studies Centre of the University of Salamanca, a teaching and research centre, began its activities as a University Centre in January 2002, although its origins date back to 1997, when a group of women professors from the University of Salamanca, interested in gender studies from their different areas of knowledge, created the Women's Studies Seminar (<https://cemusa.usal.es/>).

Description

Within the framework of the VIII Centenary of the University of Salamanca, ID ARTE and Mujeres dos Rombos present this artistic project "Rostros del Olvido" (Faces of Oblivion), which makes visible a part of all those women who studied at the University of Salamanca throughout its 800 years of history and did important work but who, unjustly, were left in the shadows.

The aim of this work was to show society some of these unknown women, forgotten and eclipsed by the predominantly male role throughout history. Starting with the twenty-two anonymous and empty medallions in the Plaza Mayor in Salamanca, this proposal aims to symbolically repair this omission, installing the interpretation made by twenty-two artists of the forgotten faces of twenty-two pioneering female students at the University of Salamanca who excelled in different disciplines.

Key achievements

To offer, through different artistic proposals, a work that passer-by-spectators can enjoy, taking art from the usual spaces such as galleries and museums to the streets.

Action tips to inspire further activities for interested parts in the field

The project takes as a reference the 22 anonymous and empty medallions in the Plaza Mayor of Salamanca, symbolically repairing them by placing in them the "forgotten faces" of 22 pioneering female students of the USAL (among many others) who excelled in their different

disciplines and who were overshadowed because of the inequalities they lived through in their times.

2.1.2. Method n.2: Think C-cubed Challenge /Mujeres que cambian la USAL

Name of the organisation/association

Scientific Culture and Innovation Unit (UCC+i) of the University of Salamanca

City, Country

Salamanca, Spain, 2023

Information about the organisation

The objectives of the Scientific Culture and Innovation Unit of the University of Salamanca include the dissemination of the scientific and technological culture produced at the University, the recognition of its scientific heritage and the promotion of scientific vocations at all educational stages.

Description

One of the main projects of the USAL's Women who change USAL is focused on presenting a group of women who are dedicated to a specific area of knowledge each year, above all they are asked to present a challenge to the students of ESO.

- Within this visibility project is the activity "Think C-cubed Challenge" where, together with the group Women who change the USAL, they bring their research in different areas of knowledge to a school audience, students of 1st ESO. The objective of promoting scientific vocations through formats close to the students remains one of

the pillars as UCC+i, each researcher is asked to launch a scientific challenge close to her area of knowledge. The participating schools compete to be the best class in solving one of the challenges, putting into practice the scientific method, and concepts such as reproducibility and refutability; but without forgetting the importance of teamwork and creativity.

- Likewise, the group Women who change USAL carries out different activities. Each activity is focused on a specific target audience. The exhibition activity that took place in 2021 focused on the adult public, so that they could get to know the women who are generating important scientific milestones and the applications that these have in their daily lives; but above all, they could get to know the contribution of the University of Salamanca to research.

Key achievements

- Make a final evaluation.
- Share the final evaluation of the activities.
- Share and show where you have failed or how successful you have been, to see if it can be replicated in another context.

Action tips to inspire further activities for interested parts in the field

The UCC+i carries out an annual programme of activities in which the participation of the members of the university community (teaching and research staff, students and administration and services staff) in the generation of contents adapted to the different publics, facilitates collaboration between the different social agents (citizens, educators, politicians, researchers, companies and other groups).

2.1.3. Method n.3: Desayuno de Mujeres Investigadoras de la Universidad de Salamanca (Breakfast of Women Researchers of the University of Salamanca)

Name of the organisation/association

Scientific Culture and Innovation Unit of the University of Salamanca

City, Country

Salamanca, Spain, 2023

Information about the organisation

The objectives of the Scientific Culture and Innovation Unit of the University of Salamanca include the dissemination of the scientific and technological culture produced at the University, the recognition of its scientific heritage and the promotion of scientific vocations at all educational stages.

Description

As part of the activities organised for the International Day of Women and Girls in Science, a breakfast for women researchers was organised. The aim was to share the experience in the scientific field, the current and future role of women and the possibilities for improvement or collaboration within the same entity. All this in a more relaxed and less academic atmosphere than usual, to learn about the situation in other disciplines and share experiences. The event was also open to male researchers who wished to attend.

The event "USAL Women Researchers Breakfast" aimed to discuss topics such as the experience in the scientific field, the role of women in science or the possibility of improvement; all in a relaxed atmosphere accompanied by a good breakfast in El Salón del Café.

Key achievements

- The idea was to get people to meet each other and talk about their research topics.
- To encourage networking, sharing, collaboration, togetherness, talking about things.
- Create informal networks to help us move forward.

Action tips to inspire further activities for interested parts in the field

To try to promote these internal contact networks between researchers at the University of Salamanca. Although the activity was a breakfast for women researchers, it was open to all women and men researchers, and all sectors of the population were represented.

2.1.4. Method n.4: Mapas de Escritoras (Women Writers' Maps)

Name of the organisation/association

The Legacy of Women

City, Country

Castilla y León, Spain, 2023

Information about the organisation

In 2019, a group of secondary school teachers from Andalucía, Asturias, Castilla y León and Valencia decided to create the National Association El Legado de las Mujeres, whose headquarters are at the IES Vaguada de la Palma in Salamanca, with the firm intention of remedying the absence of female references in secondary school textbooks and curricula. According to the study carried out at the University of Valencia by Ana López-Navajas, a member of the Association, the presence of women in these textbooks is barely 7.6%.

Description

This project of maps of women writers seeks to vindicate the inclusion of women writers, thinkers, artists and scientists in the textbooks of the different subjects contained in the curriculum and in the teaching practice of Secondary Education, in addition to recovering the legacy of women in the different fields of culture in order to rescue their names and contributions from oblivion.

Historical maps of women writers have been created for each of the autonomous communities, as an instrument to vindicate the co-protagonism of women in the cultural and social development of each region. To date, we have produced maps of Andalusia, Castile-La Mancha, Castile and Leon and Galicia. In addition, they have collaborated with a European education project, an ERASMUS+ KA201, entitled "Women's Legacy: our cultural heritage for equality", whose aim is to offer didactic intervention tools that serve to recover the forgotten European cultural heritage of female authorship and correct the androcentric vision of culture transmitted in education.

Key achievements

- Collaboration in a European education project, ERASMUS+ KA201
- Creation of historical maps

Action tips to inspire further activities for interested parts in the field

- Creation of a free online database with female references, their works and activities ready to be used in the classroom, by subject and level.
- Offer teacher training courses "The women we are missing in STEM": to include women scientists in the classroom, to be given to secondary school teachers and training advisors with a duration of 20 hours.
- Create a catalogue of musical works written by women.
- Creation of a catalogue of artistic works by women. El legado de las mujeres (LdM) will develop the contents of the database and will collaborate in the music, art and literature catalogues by proposing 15 works per catalogue.

2.2. France

2.2.1. Method n.1: «Journées du matrimoine : elles aussi ont construit la Martinique»

Union des Femmes de Martinique

City, Country

Fort-de-France, Martinique (France), September 2022

- UFM is a feminist association. The aim of this organization is to raise awareness of prevention issues relating to gender equality, violence against women, sexism, and discrimination.
- From September 12th to 30th, 2022, the association has organized an event to (re)discover women who have played a part in Martinique's social history.
- On the program: screenings of documentary films and exhibitions on women and little-known historical facts about women.

In general, the UFM often organizes screenings or events in favor of women.

Project «Matrimoine»

Culture Égalité

Culture Égalité aims to defend and promote gender equality and women's autonomy.

To make visible and raise awareness of the heritage of women and their contribution to the social, political, economic and cultural development of our society, the association (in partnership with artists) has designed original creations. These productions are available to local authorities, schools, works councils, etc. Among the creations are:

- A virtual visit: in Lumina's footsteps (<https://www.cultureegalite.fr/visite-virtuelle>)
- A theatrical reading: "1870, Femmes au Conseil de Guerre"
- A theatrical walk: "In the Roptus family, I call...". It's a theatrical three-kilometer walk in the nature during which we discover the life of Lumina Sophie, her mother Zulma and her grandmother Reine-Sophie.
- REBELLES ET MARRONNES : *Elles ont fait notre Caraïbe et les Amériques*. This historical fresco in the form of a projection honors some of the rebels and marronnes of the Caribbean and the Americas who played a major role in the struggle for freedom from the beginning of the European conquest until abolition. At the end, there's time for discussion about these female characters and, more broadly, the history of women in the Caribbean.

2.3. Cyprus

2.3.1. Method n.1: Walking tour: Making her stories visible

Name of the organisation/association.

Centre for Gender Equality and History

City, Country, 2023

Nicosia, Cyprus, 2017

Information about the organisation

Center for Gender Equality and History (KIIF) is a non-profit, non-governmental organization established in July 2017. The aim of the organisation is to promote scientific / research-based knowledge and action for gender equality. They emphasise on the empowerment of women, men, LGBTQ, and all genders. The main objective is to build a space to reclaim both past and future on the grounds of scientific knowledge, mutual respect, social justice, individual freedom, human rights, participation, democracy and equality.

Description

On Saturday, 29 October 2016, K.I.I.F. organized probably the first women's history walk ever occurred in Cyprus. Its title was Reviving the Invisible History of Women – A Walk in another

Nicosia. These were alternative “tours” seeking to make visible some aspects of women’s history in response to specific points of interest. K.I.I.F. was the first organization in Cyprus to have prepared and organized such walks.

Until today, K.I.I.F. has organized a number of women’s history walks which took place in the old city of Nicosia and have all been prepared and presented by a group of women, volunteers of K.I.I.F. Considering that women’s history in Cyprus is depressingly under-researched, the team selected the points of interest after extensive research and investigation on mainly primary sources.

Key achievements

The aim of the walks was to give the opportunity to the organizers and the public to look at the urban landscape – monuments, statues, street names etcetera – from a gendered perspective, to find elements portraying the history of gender relations and of female presence and contribution, and/or to narrate the history of Cypriot women which is depressingly invisible. In general, each individual could have a different focus.

2.3.2. Method n.2: A women's History Archive: Cyprus Library Online for Gender

Name of the organisation/association

Promitheas Research Institute, in cooperation with Centre for Gender Equality and History and the University of Cyprus

City, Country

Nicosia, Cyprus, 2019

Information about the organisation

Research Institute Promitheas was founded in 2012 to approach scientific analysis of social phenomena and through interventions and initiatives in the academic and scientific community and society. The Research Institute develops symposia, workshops, conferences and produces research, studies and academic and scientific research.

Description of the good practice (how it started, number and profile of beneficiaries, description of activities provided, region of the implementation of the initiative, people involved, financial support of the initiative, engagement of the participants, barriers and challenges, actions for continuous improvement etc.)

Description

The project “A Women’s History Archive: Cyprus Library Online for Gender” began in January 2019 and completed in December 2020. It was funded by the Research Promotion Foundation under the RESTART 2016-2020 programmes.

The first stage of the research for the online library concerns the period between 1878 and 1960. Old newspapers, interviews, archive material, photographs were concentrated in a digital online archive which is open to the public. The second stage included research aiming to examine and evaluate the potential impact of knowledge regarding women’s history on contemporary stereotypes and beliefs on gender. This stage involved a group of students with the aim of studying and evaluating the impact that knowledge on women’s history may potentially have against gender stereotypes and relevant beliefs.

Key achievements

The main aim of the project is to promote the history of women in Cyprus while tackling a series of issues: the restoration and reclamation of historical knowledge regarding women, the deconstruction of history myths and stereotypes referring to the history of genders, the demonstration of the importance of women’s contribution to the progress and development of the Cypriot society empowering and encouraging women to demand their rights and equality.

You can visit the website, here: <http://clioforgender.com/>

2.4. Greece

2.4.1. Method n.1: Women, rights and revolution

Historical background and correlation with experiences from Iran and Afghanistan/European reality

Shelter of Unaccompanied Minors of Larissa-Ministry of Migration and Asylum

City, Country

Larissa, Greece, 2023

The Shelter for Unaccompanied Children in Larissa started its operation in November 2019. The shelter accommodates unaccompanied foreign minors who have submitted a request to the respective services of the Ministry of Migration and Asylum for registration or for asylum. The above minors are provided with shelter, food, medical care, education (formal and informal), legal assistance, psychological support and, in general, any service that is of benefit to the minors themselves in order to achieve the best possible integration and inclusion in the Greek and European environment by appropriately trained and qualified staff. Specifically, legal advisors, psychologists, teachers, social workers, nursing staff, interpreters, administrative and support staff provide their services at the centre in alternating shifts, covering the needs of the minors on a 24-hour basis.

This practice was inspired by the mass protests in Iran about women's rights and the International Women's Day. The beneficiaries were a mixed group of 20 minors from different

nationalities such as Pakistan, Afghanistan, Somalia, Guinea, Guinea, Sierra Leone, Syria. It was organized and held by the shelter staff. Participants were informed about the historical elements of International Women's Day, the importance and meaning of peaceful protests, women's rights in the European world and were motivated to talk about the reactions in Iran after the death of Mahsha Amini. They expressed their feelings and shared experiences from their countries of origin and at the end they made cards with messages of support which decorated the courtyard of the Facility. Afterwards, the French-speaking beneficiaries watched the film PAPICHA at the Chatzigiannio Cultural Centre of Larissa.

Of course, the different perspectives of the beneficiaries due to their origin, religion and previous family or social experiences are often a barrier in promoting women female figures in history and in respecting gender equality. Nevertheless, the challenges of establishing a common ground can be discussed and achieved through continuous activities about gender equality, lessons about historical events that women had a crucial role and engagement with local people in activities organized by the shelter.

The participants got to know each other better, gained new knowledge, shared experiences that they had the opportunity to discuss with each other without criticism and were introduced in a way to gender equality.

Promoting female figures in history is a crucial endeavour to highlight the contributions and accomplishments of women who have shaped our world. For achieving that, there are a variety of actions that the shelter can implement. Celebrating International Women's Day is of course an important aspect, but also more activities could be organized like essay contests focused on women's history, partnership with women's organizations, engagement with art or educational events.

The shelter of unaccompanied children of Larissa and its activities is funded by the Ministry of Migration and Asylum.

2.4.2. Method n.2: Teaching Projects

Second World War

Semi-Independent Living Unit for Unaccompanied Minors-Ministry of Migration and Asylum

City, Country

Athens, Greece, 2023

The Unit of Supervised Semi-Autonomous Apartments for Minors provides an alternative form of care to unaccompanied minors recognized refugees or asylum seekers, aged 16 to 18, regardless of nationality, focusing on their gradual autonomy.

The purpose and objectives of the program and the operation of the supervised departments can be summarized in some fundamental priorities like: direct and permanent access to all health services, provision of psychosocial support services, integration in the educational environment of national public education, provision of additional intensive teaching of Greek and English language in the area of the unit, smooth integration and socialization of minors, access to constant legal support from a lawyer directly cooperating with the unit and improving beneficiaries' self-care skills.

Teaching Projects are part of the educational support that the Unit offers to beneficiaries. The goal of the projects is to expand the knowledge of the minors around historical events and link them to today's crucial events, like democracy, gender equality etc. The beneficiaries are 12 minors residing in the semi-independent apartments in the centre of Athens. The project is implemented by the educator of the Unit, who focuses on the engagement of the participants and in the expression of their thoughts and experiences. One of these projects was around the Second World War and Anna's Frank diary who depicted the cruelty of the war. Participants read parts of the diary and were shown pictures of women ponytails that

were killed by chemicals in concentration camps. This activity was important because it highlighted not only Jewish holocaust, but also the sacrifices of women and children for overthrowing the fascist regime.

Of course, diverse backgrounds and experiences of the beneficiaries are often barriers in promoting women female figures in history and fostering gender equality. However, these challenges can be addressed through continuous activities that promote understanding, empathy, and inclusivity. These activities can include open discussions about the role of women in society, promoting inclusive language, avoiding gender stereotypes and generally adapting the actions to the needs of the beneficiaries.

The participants got to know each other better, gained new knowledge, learned about the consequences of anti-Semitism and war, but also about the killing of women and children, i.e. the civilians of history.

Promoting female figures in history requires a multifaceted approach and a variety of actions to create a lasting impact. Incorporating more about women's History in the educational curriculum of the apartments is important. Also, hosting screenings of documentaries or movies that highlight the lives and achievements of influential women and hold discussions to explore the impact of these women on society is an influential suggestion.

The Semi-Independent Living Apartments of Unaccompanied Minors and its activities are funded by the Ministry of Migration and Asylum.

2.5. Bulgaria

2.5.1. Method n.1: BUDITELKITE (The Women Revivalists)

The women who change history

Name of the organisation/association.

Momichetata ot grada (The girls from the city)

City, Country

Sofia, Bulgaria, 2022

БУДИТЕЛКИТЕ

Мара Белчева – жената от моята улица

Елица Павлович

НАЙ-НОВИТЕ НАЙ-ПОПУЛЯРНИТЕ

БУДИТЕЛКИТЕ

Мара Белчева – жената от
моята улица

Елица Павлович

БУДИТЕЛКИТЕ

Яна Язова: Съдба в три
действия

Лебена Лазарова

БУДИТЕЛКИТЕ

Елисавета Консулова-Вазова –
жената, която знаела пътя към
щастие

Елица Павлович

The Girls from the City is the largest independent women's site in Bulgaria. The topics they publish about are urban culture, fashion, photography, lifestyle, literature, theatre, cinema, culinary and many more – all, inspired by women and made to inspire other women. In their own words, the collective writes their “own history, alone, with imagination and good taste”. The webpage is devoted to the positive change lead and created by women.

The specific good practice The Women Revivalists is focused on the influential women of the 19th and 20th century – writers, poets, teachers, medics, journalists, suffragists, activists, etc. The project is supported by Sofia municipality and presents each woman in an article about her life and significant accomplishments.

On 1 November 2022 the organizers created an offline event as well – they set up a photo and text exhibition at the center of Sofia and a multimedia gallery at the airport showcasing 15 prominent women, who lived and worked between 1878 and 1944 and played a key role in shaping the awareness of Bulgarian society by fostering modern democratic values: freedom, equality, dignified life, education, and culture. By creating a common memory of their role in building not only their era, but also modern Bulgarian society, the organizers spark up an honest conversation about the place of women in history and modern times.

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The multilocational and mixed media approach increased the popularity of the initiative and helped the stories of these women to reach out thousands of people, both locals and visitors of Sofia. The articles can still be found on <https://momichetata.com/>.

2.5.2. Method n.2: MEMORIAL #1

Artist/designer: Irina Tomova-Erka

Co-organizer: Bulgarian Helsinki Committee

Part of the Memorial Women campaign

Sofia, Bulgaria, 2017

The Bulgarian Helsinki Committee (BHC) is an independent, non-governmental, not-for-profit civil society organization for defending fundamental human rights in the Republic of Bulgaria: political, civil, cultural, and social. It was established in 1992. Their work consists of systematic monitoring of the situation with the human rights in Bulgaria with a specific focus on children, women, ethnic, sexual, and religious minorities, rights of people with mental, intellectual, and other disabilities, of institutions for deprivation of liberty, of freedom from discrimination, of cases of torture, inhuman, and degrading treatment, of rights of asylum seekers and migrants, of freedom of expression and of access to information, as well as issues in the criminal justice. The Bulgarian Helsinki Committee (BHC) is an independent, non-governmental, not-for-profit civil society organization for defending fundamental human rights in the Republic of Bulgaria: political, civil, cultural, and social. It was established in 1992.

This good practice started on Wednesday, March 22 2017, when Sofia dawned with seven new monuments of women, as part of an artistic action protesting the lack of monuments dedicated to women as historic figures from Bulgaria's past. The series of sculptures were created by the artist and designer Irina Tomova / Erka and carried the name MONUMENT #1. The initiative aimed to draw public attention to the fact that in Sofia there is not a single monument dedicated to a woman. Unfortunately, despite all efforts by different activists, this issue still remains.

The MEMORIAL #1 action was created supporting the Memorial Women campaign, which aimed to promote the achievements of women in our history, who fought for the affirmation of the civil and political rights of women in Bulgaria, as well as the women who paved the way for other women in the field of education, law, architecture, art, science, etc. The Memorial Women campaign was organized by the Bulgarian Helsinki Committee with the assistance of the Bulgarian Association of University Women, and the artistic action took place in partnership with the international organization for socially engaged art Fine Acts and advertising agency Tribal Worldwide Sofia.

The organizers of the campaign consulted with the Sofia Municipality to develop a clear concept for the construction of monuments dedicated to women from our history, and insisted on placing the first monument in Sofia dedicated to a female historical figure in 2018.

"The lack of monuments dedicated to real women reinforces the misconception that women do not have significant achievements or that they have not contributed to the development of a democratic society," says Svetla Baeva, director of the Campaigns and Communications program at BHC. Until the end of March 2017, everyone could support the declaration to the Metropolitan Municipality and vote in the poll for the woman who would be the first monument to commemorate, at www.womensmonth.org.

The sculptures, part of MEMORIAL #1, were all modelled after the artist's own portrait and painted in bright colours. They were placed in central locations across Sofia during a secret action early in the morning on that Wednesday. The author also drew attention to the fact that, beyond the total lack of monuments to women - historical figures, according to official data of the Metropolitan Municipal Cultural Institute, less than 6% of all memorial sites (most of which are simply memorial plaques) on the territory of the city are dedicated to women.

Immediately after the action, the sculptures were "adopted" by key institutions and galleries, including Sofia University, Sofia Library, National Library, "Peroto" Literary Club, CredoBonum Gallery, Bulgarian National Television and "Red House" Center for Culture and Debate. Until April 5, everyone was able to see the sculptures at the indicated locations. The seven sculptures were finally exhibited at an exhibition in the CredoBonum gallery in April 2017, where they were all auctioned to raise funds for the construction of the first monument to a woman - historical figure in Sofia. During the lifetime of the campaign, it gathered plenty of media attention and the monuments were visited/seen by thousands of people (citizens of Sofia, tourists, international visitors) both across the city and in the gallery.

The good practice showcased here presented a claim to the public space, which, just like history, belongs equally to women as well. There were great, inspiring women in the past of Bulgaria, but their achievements have been virtually erased. With the action, the author gave women something that is owed to them and has been denied for decades – space and recognition.

2.6. Slovenia

2.6.1. Method n.1: Exhibition, Memorial House, and Virtual Home of Alma Karin

Name of the organisation/association

Celje Regional Museum, Celje Central Library

City, Country

Celje, Slovenia, 2023

Description

An unusual woman, a being of the female gender, as Alma M. Karlin (1889-1950, Celje) called herself, a writer, world traveller, explorer, polyglot, theosophist and cosmopolitan, is an eminent Celje personality who is indelibly rooted in the memory of the city and its inhabitants. In Slovenian cultural memory, knowledge of her and awareness of her literary, research and spiritual tradition always first clashes with national prejudice - "because she was German, because she wrote in German". The time in which she grew up and matured into an individual was the age of decline and destruction of the Austro-Hungarian monarchy, and the individuality had a greater meaning for Karlin as the nationality did.

Marked with a physical defect and asymmetric eyes at birth, she was foretold a short life or a mental retardation. She remained of a fragile physical constitution for all of her life, but soon developed a high level of consciousness about herself and her aims: to understand the languages of the world, to travel worldwide, and to become an international writer. The gift for languages, which she had already developed in her informal education at home in Celje, was given a full swing during her stay in London, from 1908 to 1914, where she passed the exams from eight languages at the Royal Society of Arts. London and its Babylonian mixture of races, cultures, and languages finally confirmed her in her intention to travel the world and write about her perceptions, discoveries, and events on the way.

This resulted in the eight years long journey around the world, visiting all the continents, and living in the most distant parts of the human civilisation - about which she wrote and drew promptly with careful attention. After returning home, she wrote her renowned travelogue in three parts, *Samotno potovanje* ('The Lonely Journey'), *Doživeti svet* ('The Experienced

World'), and Urok južnega morja ('The Spell of the South Sea'), which was reprinted several times in the edition of over 100,000 copies, and was translated into the English, the Finnish, and at last also in the Slovene language. These books were followed by the others with which Alma Karlin reached at least European if not even a world fame; she was so popular in the German cultural space in the 1930s that they started establishing the Alma Karlin associations, where the supporters of her writing and her view of the world met, and the Swedish Nobel prize winner, the writer Selma Lagerlöf informally nominated her for the Nobel prize. There was no proper response to her work in Slovenia until 1960s when she was "discovered" by the Slovene ethnologists.

- The Celje Regional Museum has a permanent exhibition showing her life and her journey around the world. The life-size statue was erected in 2009.

- In Pečovnik, there is the Alma M. Karlin Memorial House, where Alma spent the last years of her life together with Theo Gammelin. It houses the permanent exhibition "The solitary journey of Alma M. Karlin".

- The Celje Central Library decided to present this unique personality in all her dimensions. Given the dynamic nature of the web, the virtual home of A.K. will have many rooms, spaces and corners. Compared to her last real home in Pečovnik above Celje, which collapsed into itself, it will be maintained, renovated and expanded.

Alma M. Karlin

Slo / Engl / Deu

How I became a human.....Round the World.....

.....Two livings - one goal.....

.....Anti-Nazi at the Partisans.....

Literary Heritage of AMK.....Spiritual Heritage of AMK...

.....The Reception of AMK at Slovenes.....

Alma M. Karlin virtual home

Alma Karlin's virtual residence will have, according to its dynamic nature, many rooms, small places, and little corners. Compared to her last true home at Pečovnik, which collapsed, this one will be maintained, renewed and extended.

For now, we are opening the door of the reception-room...

The Web Portal: <http://www.almakarlin.si/?&lang=en>

2.6.2. Method n.2: Pozoj's trail

Name of the organisation/association

Municipality of Velenje, Zavod za turizem Šaleške doline

City, Country

Velenje, Slovenia, 2023

Description

The Pozoj's Trail is a thematic trail and a book entitled Pozoj's Castle Trail around Velenje and a leaflet have been published to promote the trail. The trail was marked with signposts and information boards, and a mascot of Pozo was created. Visitors to the trail receive a stamp at each point. Once they collected all five stamps, they receive a special sticker from the Velenje Tourist Information Centre. A "treasure hunt" can be organised for young families, and an electronic tourist guide can be used to guide tourists along the Pozoj's Trail.

The map and activity

The Pozoj's Castle Trail connects five attractions around Velenje. These include the imposing Velenje Castle, which proudly towers over the young town, the nostalgic castles of Šalek, Ekenštejn and Turn, and the area of the sunken Škale, which was once the centre of the Šaleška Valley. Other sights, marked on the map in the guidebook, also catch the eye along the way.

The starting point and the end of the trail is Vila Bianca. There is a Tourist Information Centre (TIC) where you pick up a card for collecting stamps. Look for these on the presentation boards at each attraction. As the stamps need to be rubbed, take a pen with you. If you manage to visit all five sites, you will have collected five stamps. At the TIC, when you present

the card with all the stamps, you will receive a prize - a Pozo sticker, which you stick in the box at the end of the guide. The guidebook, which is small enough to fit in your pocket or backpack, also accompanies you on your journey.

The trail can be walked in its entirety and cycled in most parts.

The Story of Pozoj

The lake's Pozoj (dragon) is a mythological creature. Pieces of coal have been found on the edge of the Šaleška valley, looking out into the day. Coal used to be called dragon's blood and where there is dragon's blood, there must be a dragon. People believed that the dragon was hatched from a red egg laid by a seven-year-old rooster. This egg just plunges into an underground lake in the middle of the mountain, where the *pozoj* grows up, breaks through the mountain face in a violent storm and comes to the surface, as Špela Poles wrote in her guidebook.

About the Project

The Pozoj's Trail project is part of the Custodes project, which aimed to develop lesser-known tourist destinations in Europe. The municipality of Velenje has joined the project as a Valley of Castles.

The Website: <https://www.visitsaleska.si/sl/products/pozojeva-grajska-pot/>

2.7. Lithuania

2.7.1. Method n.1: Women who built Lithuania (org. Moterys, kūrusios Lietuvą)

Name of the organisation/association:

Vilnius yra mokykla

City, Country

Vilnius, Lithuania, 2023

Information about the organisation

“Vilnius yra mokykla” (en. “Vilnius is a school”) is a project run by the education agency of Vilnius municipality “EDU Vilnius” and Vilnius municipality. The aim of this project is to seek for modernity in the education system – to move at least 10 percent of lessons from classrooms to the different spaces of the city and to apply a mixed education model combining traditional lessons with lessons in the city.

Description

“Women who built Lithuania” is an integrative ethics-history lesson which aims to change the stereotypes about the historical influence of women on the political, cultural, and public life of Lithuania. During the lessons schoolchildren learn not only about the women who were mothers, wives, or daughters of better-known men, but also who were active members of our society, brought changes and contributed to building cultural and national self-awareness, as well as fought for women’s rights.

During the lesson students are divided into groups and visit all the places indicated on the map (in total 6 places). They have to find out the identity of the woman in whose honour a monument or memorial plaque is built at that place. After finding the specified place, the students have to write the name of the woman they found in the empty spaces of the map. After finishing the first task, they look for clues for the second task.

After visiting all the indicated places on the map, students have to find out what kind of woman is described in the second task (Task No. 2). Students are warned that there is one additional description, thus, they will have to guess who this woman is.

After completing all the activities, students have to share their ideas about who could be those three women that should have their monuments or memorial boards in Vilnius city (Task No.3). The ideas are presented for the classmates.

Target group: Schoolchildren of 9th-10th grade

Venue: Lesson takes place in the old town of Vilnius city

Duration: 1 hour 30 minutes

Financial support: education agency of Vilnius municipality "EDU Vilnius"

How it started: The idea came up very naturally as for the initiator of the lessons are important to talk with school children on the topics that are in the margins.

Barriers and challenges

- In general lack of information about women who put a contribution to the history of our society
- Lack of methodological material for teachers on such topic, teachers have to show their initiative if they want to find additional information to introduce for the schoolchildren (it costs time and can require additional financial resources to collect the material that is needed)

Actions for continuous improvement

To find out the personalities that would encourage you to read more and to be interested (such as Marina Abramović, Yoko Ono, etc.).

Action tips to inspire further activities for interested parts in the field

- To find ways to engage students into activities. One of the inspirations could be to involve into the content the personalities that could surprise, are unknown, but could be interesting for a young person. When a young person is surprised, (s)he is more willing to be interested and dig deeper to the provided information.

- To focus on the personalities the students met each and who are in their surrounding at present moment. For example, first to talk about who are mothers or grandmothers of the students and they can realize that they have examples that can inspire just behind them.

2.8. Italy

2.8.1. Method n.1: Porcospini Project

Name of the organisation/association

Cooperativa sociale Specchio Magico (Luisa Bono – HerStory stakeholder)

Specchio Magico was founded in May 2001 by the will of charter members of sharing their own competences through a cooperating project. Specchio Magico has a wide area of expertise, ranging from education, training, active citizenship, inclusion, educational and pedagogical methodologies and approaches for early childhood, children youngsters as well as from preventing domestic and sexual violence to effective interventions in the social sector. The organization also promotes intervention on schools, which represent a big part of the activities developed cooperating with school institutions and integrated in the right to study plan of each school. Specchio Magico is a not-for profit organization.

Specchio Magico, after initial years devoted to strengthen territorial networks, started implementing European project activities in order to share and implement training and education activities at international and European level.

“**Porcospini**”’s goal is to contribute to the evolution of a global and integrated policy of primary prevention and opposition to the phenomenon of bullying, cyberbullying and gender-based violence (GBV) related to web and social media risks.

“Porcospini”, as its name underlines, is based on Education, Equality and Evolution. The E of Evolution is deeply based on over ten years of experiences on Porcospini/Hedgehogs, with more than 40,000 children and families involved, including children from 5 years old to 14

years old, teachers and professionals directly engaged in the field. The Evolution of Porcospini is the adaptation of the model of intervention to the new challenges represented by the invasive spreading of the Internet and social media into the daily lives of children and the rise of new needs and risks such as online hate speech, cyberbullying, sexting, and revenge porn. “Porcospini” intends to encourage the implementation of activities such as raising awareness, providing information and running training, including in IT, in primary and secondary schools. The model of intervention aims to: equip children with the necessary tools to make them aware of their body and emotions, teaching them how to identify and listen to them; make children feel in the right when expressing their questions and investigating their growth; develop a preventive intervention solution, enhancing the wellbeing of the local community, promoting accurate, complete and non-alarmist information; help children in developing critical skills to identify and react against potential risk situations, so as to avoid exposure to the risk itself by choosing the most appropriate protection strategies; promote children’s abilities of self-assertion and self-determination by acting on the construction and enhancement of their identity; Children who benefit from the participation to the Porcospini project acquire knowledge that helps them in the short term and that will help them to protect themselves in the future, abilities in terms of protection competencies that are useful for rejecting a potential abuser.

This project, aimed at preventing child maltreatment and abuse, provides young people with a toolkit where key tools are self-esteem, critical thinking, self and hetero-narration, problem-solving, and emotional intelligence. The goal is to create new models through primary prevention interventions.

2.8.2. Method n.2: SifaSTEM

Name of the organisation/association etc:

Soroptimist Women's Association (Fulvia Greppi- HerStory Stakeholder)

Soroptimist is a worldwide association of women engaged in professional and managerial activities, a universal voice for women that expresses itself through awareness, support and action. Soroptimist supports Human Rights for All, world peace and international goodwill, women's potential, transparency and democratic decision-making, acceptance of diversity, sustainable development, volunteerism and friendship. Soroptimists carry out projects, promote actions, and create opportunities through the global network of members and international cooperation so that all women can realize their individual and collective potential, realize their aspirations, and create strong peaceful communities around the world.

SifaSTEM is an initiative carried out, in May 2023, by Soroptimist Club Lecco, with the Province of Lecco, the leading body for orientation ICS Lecco, and the Territorial School Office, at the Monastery of "Santa Maria del Lavello". It was a university orientation seminar towards scientific and technological subjects. The event was attended by the girls of the 3^o and 4^o of the "Lorenzo Rota Institute" in large numbers as well as some students from other secondary schools of Lecco.

SifaSTEM project aims to break down gender bias with respect to scientific subjects. The aim is to increase the number of girls in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics), helping them to make informed choices not dictated by concepts and stereotypes of society.

Many speakers have taken part to the initiative, men and women, who shared with the students their experience and offered them ideas and varied reflections. Among them:

- Anna Gilardi, graduating in building engineering and architecture and Sophie Patras who attends the master's degree in "Civil Engineering and Risk Mitigation" both at the Milan Polytechnic, Lecco territorial pole, have transmitted their passion for engineering by showing examples of concrete applications of their studies to the protection and conservation of the beautiful works that surround us;
- Paolo Nespoli, aerospace engineer, former astronaut of the European Space Agency and professor at the Milan Polytechnic, encouraged young students to follow their dreams and passions, whatever they are, because it is the prerogative for a life of satisfaction;
- Magda Fontanella, graduated in philosophy of the person and bioethics, stressed the importance of constantly asking questions about one's personal and work satisfaction, and how following a philosophical path does not preclude being able to work in the scientific field, as for example in her case, where philosophy is applied daily in the medical field;
- Chiara Brombin, professor of statistics at the Faculty of Psychology of the Vita-Salute San Raffaele University, explained that digital alters the perception that young people have of themselves, especially when using the "filters" proposed by apps and social media;
- Simone Terreni, through the story of women who in the past have left their mark, leading us into today's digital age, highlighted the strength of the female gender and how it has been and is fundamental in society.

2.8.3. Method n.3: Spazio Stupidero

Name of the organisation/association

"L'Isola della Stupidera" Association (Alessandra Maggi – HerStory Stakeholder)

L'Isola della Stupidera is a social promotion association that organizes spaces for meeting and animation. Involving males in educational and caregiving activities allows for broadening perspectives: discussing women's issues is not solely for women. Together, they seek to build alternative models based on concrete and daily commitment.

The "Spazio Stupidero" has been created by the "Isola della Stupidera" boys and girls, thanks to the collaboration established with the Municipality; the Association is a space that, in some time slots of the week, is open to accommodate children aged 6 to 10 years and offer them play services, creative workshops and coaching in the study, thanks to the presence of qualified animators and volunteers, with experience in education. The "Stupideri" – as the members of the association born in Olginate in 2016 like to call themselves and since then engaged in the organization of original "child-friendly" events – intend to propose themselves as facilitators of the encounter between generations, putting in place, in addition to individual initiatives, more structured projects with the desire and ambition to open spaces for dialogue starting from "doing together". It is with this in mind that in the coming weeks new workshops will start – dedicated to Primary School children, but also to older students – with innovative technological solutions taken directly from robotics: the goal is to bring children closer to

science and instil in them curiosity towards a world from which, with good probability, the professions of the future will be derived. As mentioned, the objectives of the project are certainly ambitious: to implement systematic learning paths in a climate of integration and inclusion, to facilitate the development of metacognitive skills, to enhance individual cultural and social specificities and to encourage motivation to study, supporting the processes of transformation and growth and encouraging moments of socialization among peers.

2.8.4. Method n.4: HerStory stakeholders job experiences

Name of the organisation/association

HerStory Stakeholders

Mayor - Paola Colombo. Holding such a public office allows for listening to the needs of citizens and taking active action for the public good. It is particularly relevant to focus on the youth, offering them new opportunities and growth experiences. Moreover, the role of schools and education is crucial, as they accompany individuals' growth not only in the academic dimension but also, and above all, in the educational and formative aspect.

Professional experience as a councilor/local government advisor - Marina Calegari. Working in the public context requires and promotes the development of social skills, empathy, listening, and effective communication. Working in teams, where men and women cooperate constantly, allows the creation of various teams: dialogue and confrontation become tools for personal as well as professional growth.

Social Worker - Romina Papini. Working in the public sector allows offering support and assistance to anyone who seeks it, to any woman who desires guidance in learning to be a mother. Social activities, where different professional figures come together, require constant work in creating a network. These connections can also be a resource for growth, comparison, and self-assertion, while breaking the web of competition.

2.8.5. Method n.5: Lecco Film Fest

Name of the organisation/association

Fondazione Ente dello Spettacolo e promossa da Confindustria Lecco e Sondrio

Fondazione Ente dello Spettacolo promotes film culture in Italy by proposing itself as a space for reflection and mediation and meanings. Criticism, training, planning, communication, organization of events, workshops, reviews and festivals: with its activities, the Foundation oversees every area concerning cinema in Italy and abroad, representing an authoritative point of reference for fans and for all those who want to approach the world of cinema for cultural deepening, personal growth, business development. Fondazione Ente dello Spettacolo pursues the goal of educating the younger generations to a critical look, offering them the tools to be able to deepen and interpret more and more consciously the characteristics, structures and senses of audiovisual language.

The **Lecco Film Fest**, born in 2019, has resulted, since the first edition, as an innovative festival in the Italian panorama for the content and languages used, as it proposed an all-female look at the world of cinema, culture and society. The Lecco Film Fest is not a festival on the female world but a space for female narration, transversal to all the areas in which women bring their fundamental contribution.

"Luci della città" is the title of the third edition, indicating the ability of culture in general and of the cinematographic proposal in particular to illuminate individuals and communities. The

meetings, the debates, the reflections that will be expressed, the films that will be screened are points of light for Lecco.

In continuity with past editions, the female gaze remains as an element that transversely reads the topics of the day, that is, it is assumed as a reading of phenomena in a dialogical relationship with the complex world of Italian cinema.

The format includes meetings with the protagonists of the world of cinema, film screenings with an introduction by the director, masterclasses and a training course for students.

2.8.6. Method n.6: Il ritratto di Bellano

Artist

Carlo Borlenghi e Andrea Vitali

The Bellano photographer **Carlo Borlenghi** is known all over the world for action photography, in particular for sailing images, from the America's Cup to the most important international regattas. Those who know his beginnings, however, remember his black and white images dedicated to the village and its inhabitants. During the pandemic, Borlenghi, forced by the impossibility of traveling, began to study the art of portraiture and posed his family in his home study. Curiosity and voracity did the rest: over 8000 shots – among these 1500 were selected – made asking people to be themselves, in a look of reciprocity and absolute honesty that leaves no room for interpretation.

The **portrait of Bellano** is the photograph of a village on Lake Como that is told through the faces of over a third of its 3500 inhabitants. The project collects portraits of those who live in Bellano but also of those who work there, of those who have made it their chosen place or of those who Bellanese aspire to be.

Between March and August 2022, the photographer set up a set in Piazza Santa Marta while the writer did his best to draw up lists of people to be traced so that they could accept the invitation to be part of this great fresco that in the results seems to wink, or even knock on

the door of the Guinness Book of Records: a book divided into alphabetical chapters, introduced by short texts, often aphorisms, by Andrea Vitali, where the faces are combined with the surnames of the families who have taken root here in the past to the present day; and is accompanied by an exhibition, curated by the artist Velasco Vitali, which from December 2022 to March 2023 invades over 400 shop windows, offices, public spaces and streets.

The project involved 1,500 Bellano and aspiring Bellano people, 8,000 shots from which the almost 900 photos included in the book (450 pages) were chosen and exhibited in over 400 public spaces around the country (over 700 square meters of covered surfaces).

A delivery to the present future of a place that the inhabitants consider the most beautiful in the world.

The portrait of Bellano tries to restore to the country and the territory that role of protagonist and natural center that has made it over the centuries a place of cooperation, work, civil instances and celebration, in close relationship with the landscape that welcomes it.

Carlo, with his reportage of looks, has set up a study to reach those who wanted to respond to the appeal to "be there", to silently emphasize with their presence the purpose of the project, that of living in a present time, to be a testimony. Here and now.

All those who have posed for him, who have sat in front of his camera, will all be able to see that human nature has an even greater soul when it is shared, that community life is activated when it is participatory. The condition is to put our face on it, proven certainty that we exist.